

ISic1385

I.Sicily inscription 1385

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo S. Nicolai

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140891

1. [— — —]ΚΟΙΠΑΣ [— —]

2. [— —]ΛΑ ἡγορ [— —]

3. [— — —]ΛΙΟ[— — —] {²⁷ἡγορ[ά] | [σατ]ο (Kirchhoff)}²⁷

4.

Edition: PHI140892

1. [— — —] κο[ῦ]πας [— —]

2. [— —]ΛΑ ἡγόρ [ασεν — —]

3. [— — ἰδ]ίο [ις — — —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492999

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PHI 140891

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Bibliography

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